

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

First Cycle Evaluation Report

WP7_D7.3

Version 1

H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2016

Grant Agreement number: 727066

1st November 2016 – 30th September 2019

First Cycle Evaluation Report

Deliverable number WP7_D7.3

Deliverable description			
Filename	WYRED_WP7_D7.3_version.1		
Type	R		
Dissemination level	PU		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.2621865		
Due Date (in months)	M24		
Deliverable contributors			
Version No.	Name, Institution	Role	Last update
1	Paul Butler, PYE Global	author	21 /03 / 2019

* cfr. GA – Annex I Part A – 1.3.2 WT2 – list of deliverables

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1. Introduction

This report sets out to provide an interpretation of the results of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) over its initial two cycles (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b). Each cycle has involved the implementation of the WYRED methodological steps.

The WYRED methodological approach involves a series of linked phases, beginning with a **consultation phase** involving outreach and engagement work and a social dialogue process. In this initial step, the children and young people are brought together and facilitated to examine digital society issues and concerns, using age appropriate facilitation techniques and tools. This work leads to a second **phase of research definition**. Through the articulation of research questions, the children and young people are again supported to consider the key issues in more depth. The next stage in the process involves an action dimension. The research question becomes articulated as a research project. This can take a wide range of forms, from the development of a video response, a podcast discussion, journaling or blogging, through to the writing of poetry. These projects are then analysed in the final phase. The children young people look to interpret their work, their responses and attribute further meaning to these phases of work. At each phase, the children and young people are being empowered to present their own analysis and critique of the online environment with which they are dealing.

Young people's opinions are frequently seen (or characterised) as simply individual views, and therefore not representative. There is a need to show evidence for their perspectives if they are to have an influence. The WYRED project aims to help young people research the digital issues that matter to them, so that their concerns are backed up with evidence, so that they can have an influence (Griffiths et al., 2017).

WYRED aims to

- amplify youth voices
- strengthen youth views through youth-led research
- connect youth with decision-makers
- broaden understanding of the digital society
- make youth perspectives matter

Cycle 1 focused on the testing of this methodology with children and young people across the full partnership. This cycle led to the engagement of over 500 children and young people in a consultative process, leading in turn to 280 of these participating in almost 100 separate projects. An online platform was developed to allow the sharing of these local projects and promote an engagement between the target groups and key policy stakeholders, from education, youth work and community sectors. Cycle 2 allowed for further iterations of the methodological steps. Partners have again reached out to over 500 children and young people in consultative forums, facilitating conversations and discussions regarding perceptions about their online lives. Through these social dialogues, a further set of 58 research questions were elaborated, leading to 50 projects with almost 300

children and young people. Again, these projects have led to the sharing of responses and presentations of solutions to commonly faced challenges within the platform and elsewhere.

Partners were focused on an examination of themes and topics of interest to children and young people related to digital society issues. The priority for WYRED projects was to draw out recommendations or conclusions from the children and young people around their chosen research projects and topics of interest.

In order to surface these insights, the children and young people were facilitated to evaluate their own projects through a range of creative methods, informal and dynamic approaches, as well as specifically tailored toolkits. These self-administered processes assisted the children and young people to identify the value and relevance of what they had been doing within WYRED activities. This was also a core element of the WYRED approach in ensuring that children and young people would be active in this process through choosing the messages, formats and channels that they regard as most appropriate to present their results, in relation to what it is that they want to explain and how they would present this. Evaluation toolkits were available for partners to implement and tailor in their local environments.

This report is structured in two parts.

- Sections 2-3 present evaluation results from cycle one and two, with quantitative and qualitative overviews of key themes and lessons learnt. A series of case studies are detailed to further illustrate the successful application of the WYRED methodology.
- Section 4 is then focused on an analysis of insights as they have emerged, especially in relation as to the voices of the children and young people have shaped these understandings of digital society.

2. Overview of Results

Much of the activity base of Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 involved creative projects and actions by children and young people in response to a particular question or issue pertaining to their online lives and wider digital society concerns. A research and evaluation toolkit (including templates and guidelines) was developed for the facilitators to support and guide the process. All partners in turn made use of this toolkit while facilitating research activities.

During the 1st Cycle of the project, each partner organisation engaged with children and young people in their local contexts. These settings included the formal, from primary and second level schools, to training institutes and third level colleges. Informal and non-formal sectors were also selected, including youth services and centres and youth cafes.

Having attended online sessions and webinars that allowed for development of a co-ordinated and shared approach to the design, delivery and review steps within the WYRED cycle, the facilitators began their engagement with the children and young people by examining themes and creating a space for social dialogues.

The participants were supported and encouraged to start conversations and develop a series of questions that they would like to further address. Not all questions were selected for the next step, but the most pertinent became the focus for research projects and activities that were then undertaken either within groups or individually. The voice of the children and young people was critical within this process. The process was framed by their interests and priorities. As they became more involved in the WYRED cycle, they also engaged in self-evaluation and collected feedback with their facilitators as to helping and hindering factors.

Furthermore, individuals and groups were able to present their ongoing work as public projects in the common area in the WYRED platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, García-Holgado, & Seoane-Pardo, 2019), and in the respective community areas created for them by the partner organisations. Participants were encouraged to read and review projects developed by other children and young people within the platform. Participants were supported to compare and contrast their experiences with projects run by peers across participating countries, covering a variety of topics in English and/or in local languages.

The following diagram explains these four stages of the cycle from both perspective of partner and participant (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b).

Through both phases of the WYRED cycle, the consortium has facilitated a wide range of exploratory research activities, during which groups of children and young people, internationally or locally, have investigated and examined issues that concern them in the digital arena. They have been supported to do this through creative projects (e.g. prototyping solutions following an ideation session to tackle pre-defined challenges) or more conventional research projects. Interaction during the research activities has taken place both on the dedicated platform as well as through other media. Each group that is working on a research activity administers its own space on the platform to record and review work progress.

The initial engagement with the children and young people takes place through an outreach and social dialogue phase. To date, this has involved:

- Cycle 1: 32 Social dialogue sessions with 550 Children and Young People
- Cycle 2: 76 Social dialogue sessions with 538 Children and Young People

Once engaged, facilitators have worked with the children and young people, using the WYRED Activity Toolkit to assist them in elaborating research questions and projects. Each project in turn generates a series of research artefacts. To date, this has involved

- Cycle 1: 438 active participants involved in generating 101 research projects and associated artefacts
- Cycle 2: 414 active participants involved in generating 43 research projects and associated artefacts

Cycle 3 activities are ongoing across the partnership.

3. Key Themes Emerging- Case Studies

Through both cycles of the WYRED project, the consortium has facilitated a wide range of exploratory research activities, during which groups of children and young people, internationally or locally, have investigated and examined issues that concern them in the digital arena. They have been supported to do this through creative projects (e.g. prototyping solutions following an ideation session to tackle pre-defined challenges) or more conventional research projects.

Interaction during the research activities has taken place both on the dedicated platform as well as through other media. Each group that is working on a research activity administers its own space on the platform to record and review work progress.

Through the initial cycles of the WYRED project, the children and young people were the key drivers of the thematic focus. Their voice was facilitated to articulate the direction of their research interests. The focus of the research activities has been consistently trained on the lens of the digital society and how they are relating to its reach in their lives.

The main themes that were of interest to the children and young people have been grouped accordingly across each cycle. Emerging from the first cycle of activities, the children and young people had identified the following themes and discussion points as important interests.

Cycle 1 Themes	Issues and Insights from Cycle 1 Activity Base
1. Internet & Security	Self-awareness by children and young people about the Internet and its relation with their self-image and relationship with parents and adults. The young people need to face the challenge of being themselves in both real and digital world, and nobody is instructing them with regard to living in their digital environments. The space/limits between online and offline world is not so clear; Not a lot of young people are aware of dangers and “rights” when it comes to the digital world.
2. Internet & Social Media	Awareness about social media channels and how youth interact through these channels; Dangers and social implication identified by young people and proposal of solutions for a healthy relationship with online life. Relevance of how children and young people express and communicate through these channels. Youth need education or guidance on how to use and interpret images that constantly circulate and receive on social media
3. Digital society/ world	Children and young people tend to be ignored when creating policies and processes that have a direct impact on them (online or offline); There is lack of education and development of critical thinking in relevance to the digital world; The digital world might not be tangible but affects mind-sets, culture and language; The online spaces seem to be more engaging rather offline/adult spaces; Not being heard by society leads to “speaking up” online and using that to share frustrations and connect to people
4. Environment pollution	Awareness of world environmental issues and claim of International organisations action
5. Education	Strong criticism around education system that generates strong frustration for students and demotivation regarding their aspirations and future. Overload of school and after school duties. A change in school curricula is needed. Education is about how to live, not about just information and contents (which can be easily founded on the Internet). Emotional education is seen as key to succeed in this (twofold) world. Importance and need to incorporate more technology education in the curricula and access to technology.

6. Self-image	The individual is beyond the concepts of both Nation and Global. The self-image is challenging, but the other two concepts tend to be fuzzy
7. Wellbeing & Health	Relevance of self-care. How yoga, education and society, and the different issues that young people are concerned about which include substance abuse, creativity, anger issues, media and others, but the most important shared concerns were the state of education, the state of the environment, and issues relating to mental health. Reasons of being stressed - pressure in nowadays societies and the role
8. Bullying	Schools should have a more direct role in terms of inclusion, support and direct confrontation Importance of the role of teachers as mentors and need of more training on this issue
9. Politics	Interest in the topic however the level of participation in elections is very low. Need more active engagement from civil society in politics and on the other side, institutions need to focus more on youth needs & demands, as they don't feel represented by any group
10. Employment	Youth lack of interest and information about the actual labour situation and social and political consequences, however the high unemployment rates persist. Youth ask for revisions and reform of hiring processes, training programs, revisions of labour laws and contracts to improve workers conditions
11. Culture and identity	Reflexion around culture and identity and the impact of stereotypes and prejudices on the mind-set of young people; Prevention programs are necessary to prevent problems around racism, discrimination and political troubles; More initiatives/policies to promote an inclusive ecosystem (cultural, religion, sex orientation, languages, etc.

The children and young people were supported and facilitated to train their lens in a more targeted manner, allowing for the more specific themes to emerge. As the WYRED methodology was implemented again through the second cycle, facilitators encouraged the young people to explore a range of themes that were more and more connected to their digital lives.

Cycle 2 Themes	
Self-image and its presentation online	Media literacy
Gender discrimination, and gender differences online	Impact of hyper-connectivity and IoE on the individual
Stereotyping in online contexts	Digital activism
Internet safety	Future of employment in a digital world
Internet privacy	Changes in education in a digital world
Cyber security	Tolerance of different cultures, and integration of migrants
Living on social media	Living with stress online
Access to reliable information, and fake news	Digital divide
New technologies and their impacts on different field in the future	Cyberbullying and online abuse

Through this iterative process of again evaluating all research activities, these themes have again been reviewed through the Cycle 2 research process.

This section now seeks to demonstrate how these themes were examined in a range of case studies, facilitated by each of the partners. These examples evidence the manner in which the methodological process has surfaced the voices of children and young people in each country. These themes were explored in a wide range of settings, from the formal spaces of primary and second level classrooms, third level institutes and universities, through to the informal environments of youth centres and youth groups.

Each case study demonstrates that the methodological approach has a wide applicability and generates meaningful responses in each of these settings. The social dialogues prove to be important opportunities for the children and young people to begin their engagement with overarching themes and often meta-level analysis of their positions within a digital world.

As their particular interests become more to the fore, often age-related or linked to their educational backgrounds, the process facilitates further and more detailed exploration. They can then set out questions or hypotheses that they would like to answer or understand better. They are supported to access research tools and methods by their teachers, facilitators and youth workers. However, by this stage in the methodology, the children and young people have taken full control of the process. The adults become part of the background, only to be become relevant when asked for some assistance.

These elements of embracing autonomy, clearly articulating goals and rationales for doing research, as well as the desire to share their results and outcomes are to be found in each case study. Irrespective of age, context or educational background, the children and young people all when given the opportunity “gladly took the keys of the car and expertly drove it” (as described by one facilitator).

The more specific themes as arrived at in the second cycle, also represented the desire of the children and young people to engage in a focused manner with the challenges and opportunities that digital society was presenting to them.

The following case studies have been selected:

Case Study 1: Boundaries- “How can yoga help young people in the digital age?”

A group of young people were interested in how positive mental health outcomes can be promoted through introducing yoga into schools. The research results had incredible reach, with the group presenting their recommendations to politicians in the House of Lords, as well as to delegates at a major national conference.

Case Study 2: Doga- “Democracy in Schools”

Second level students in Istanbul explored how schools can become more responsive and democratic. Structured interviews were held with a cross section of students in different schools. These interviews were videoed and produced as one element of the research artefacts. A detailed report presents guidelines and tools for schools.

Case Study 3: Early Years Organisation- “Children Examining “Fake” News”

This group was the youngest set of participants within Cycle 2 of the WYRED project. However, despite their young age (9-10 years old), they present a very sophisticated analysis and questioning of how various media can operate to create confusion. They presented their findings to the whole school community and parents.

Case Study 4: MOVES- “Reflections on My Life”

This project worked with a group of teenagers in a school that works with young people, for whom the mainstream system has not been a fit. A specific young person was supported to work through the WYRED methodology with empowering outcomes. This young person produced a series of thoughtful reflections regarding her life. From the facilitator: “For me this is the most valuable project I facilitated in WYRED, because I saw her growing in WYRED, she reflected on herself and her life and got taller with every new research meeting we had.”

Case Study 5: Oxfam Italy- “Responding to Globalisation and Self-Representation in the Digital Society”

This group of third level students were engaged in an in-depth study of the impacts of globalisation on their community. This application of the WYRED methodology led to 15 projects, carried out by 17 young people, with more than 300 young people engaged through the research approaches, whether through interviews or being participants within surveys.

Case Study 6: Partners for Youth Empowerment- “Housing and homelessness within our community”

The setting for this project represents a similar space as the Austrian case study. Once again, a key impact of the application of the methodology on a one-to-one basis was the empowering of a young person, who ordinarily would not have been facilitated through this combination of participatory action research and youth work. This young person was particularly interested in the issue of homelessness in his community. Through the research project, he raised awareness of the challenges facing many young people in relation to housing precarity.

Case Study 7: TAU- “How to shape a better future for the Israeli society”

A large group of students were brought together as part of a summer programme to encourage young people from disadvantaged areas to consider their third level educational futures. The WYRED steps were used to promote an analysis as to how many social and urban conditions influence decision-making. The group produced a range of research outputs, including videos.

Case Study 8: USAL- “Globalisation, the nation and the individual in today's world”

A large group of high school students worked within their classes on the development of 36 separate projects based on the themes of globalisation and the individual. Teachers and facilitators came together to support the process in a high school. The key success factor in this project related to the fact that “students felt very involved in the research experience, free to express their opinions and to choose the language and the tools to do it. After the first approach tutored by the teachers in the face to face session, they worked autonomously with excellent results.” One particular project was presented at the European Youth Event, hosted in June 2018 in the European Parliament in Strasbourg. During the event, 9,000 participants discussed their ideas for the future of Europe with decision makers.

Case Study 9: YEU- “Brave New You”

Almost 100 young people were brought together through a YEU programme that was based on the promotion of “a tolerant and open-minded society that perceives its differences as enriching power and distinctive advantage”. These young people were spread across 11 countries and produced research in each. Many of these were linked to themes regarding cyberbullying, online abuse and conflicts. The research also looked to how online spaces and tools can work positively to bring people together.

3.1 Case Study- Boundaries- How can yoga help young people in the digital age?

PROFILE OF BOUNDARIES

Boundaries focuses on developing new approaches to social research. The organisation carries out research that looks at different facets of social change, especially around technology and how people interact with it. The research is concerned with moving beyond current approaches to policy analysis that tend to ignore the deep aspects of human experience, focussing on behavioural change produced by technological implementation, at the expense of more nuanced exploration of changes in underlying understandings.

Much of Boundaries' work focuses on the proactive inclusion of third party stakeholders, and the creation and cultivation of the community of participants. The staff of Boundaries have extensive careers in social, educational and systems research and in sustainability and intercultural issues.

Within WYRED, the Boundaries team are working within second level schools and youth spaces, where young people are participating in creative and cultural activities. This particular project brought together 12 young people aged between 13 and 18 years old and focused on their shared interest in yoga and how this can assist them in dealing with their online lives.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

The group had formed initially around an interest in yoga and were motivated to look at how they could in turn share this interest with other young people. The WYRED process was to provide a useful mechanism for their message. The young people were facilitated to work through the WYRED steps and as a result become very important youth advocates for the promotion of yoga within education at a local and national level.

The introduction of the WYRED methodology and planning of the research work took place over a series of online and face to face sessions. These initial sessions focused largely on the social dialogue phase. The young people worked together on a process of group and individual reflection, exploring and sharing their own experience of yoga and how it had changed their lives.

One of the facilitators described the manner in which the group worked successfully together, highlighting how from the outset that a strong bond had formed within the group, as well as committed work ethic.

"In general, the sessions went very well. What is perhaps especially valuable was that after the initial setting up of the meeting and some orientation, the group was very self-organising. This meant that after helping to initiate the process, I was able to step back from the process, and the young people worked autonomously, which they did very effectively"

The young people were clear from the social dialogue phase that their research question and project would be action-focused. Their vision for change was clear at these early phases of the methodology.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Following on from the social dialogue sessions, a series of workshops were facilitated over the course of a weekend meeting of the group. Each of these sessions lasted two hours. In these, the group members continued on their initial work through further examining their personal experiences and their stories regarding yoga, well-being, social media and education. Through examining these individual stories and extracting lessons from them, they were able to work out the potential commonalities across the group.

As a research question and strategy was being formulated, it was becoming clear to the group that the focus of their research energies would be on the education sector and how the practice of yoga could be integrated within schools. A further aspect of the research would be on collecting learning regarding the potential impacts of yoga in relation to mental health.

The initial self-directed approach to the work continued through this research planning phase. A facilitator again pointed to the importance of the young people taking the lead as they planned their project.

As the young people were based in different areas, they included in their planning the need to use online tools to chat and discuss their shared approaches.

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

Further sessions were facilitated as required via Skype or through face to face meetings, allowing for the young people to organise and co-ordinate their research work. A key research element was a survey of attitudes to yoga carried out in a school of on the group participants. Through this survey, they explored how yoga, education and society overlap. Those surveyed focused on a wide range of factors that they as young people are concerned about including substance abuse, creativity, anger management, media and other issues. The most important shared concerns related to the state of education, the state of the environment, and issues relating to mental health.

The research team came together to focus on their research analysis, work on conclusions and the preparation of the presentation of their results. A key aspect of their set of recommendations was the development of their “blueprint” for yoga in schools. This blueprint for yoga in schools was structured as a shared vision as to how yoga could be incorporated into a school curriculum.

The innovative approach taken by the young people, leading to their research findings and blueprint were recognised at a national level within the UK, when they were invited to make a presentation at a yoga and education conference in London. Each of the young people spoke about their own personal reasons for coming to yoga, and their research recommendations, in the form of the blueprint, were presented.

A facilitator highlighted this outcome and how they had developed key competences beyond research skills.

“In a later session, I was invited in to help work out how best the conclusions they had reached could be presented. This was done for a conference on education wellbeing and yoga, where the young people presented each personal story and their blueprint for yoga in schools. They had worked together to prepare the session themselves, and as a result of that process, they realised they wanted to continue to work together to share their experiences and help promote yoga for young people. During the session at the conference they set out their vision for the incorporation of yoga in schools so that all young people can have access to the benefits of yoga as they have.”

Their presentations were extremely well received at this large annual conference of practitioners and educational experts, with feedback received by the organisers indicating that their input was the most successful session of the conference. The blueprint has continued to be refined and developed, with the young people playing an important role in shaping these ongoing steps. The young people have gone on to present their blueprint to policymakers and decision makers, including within an All Party Parliamentary Group within the British House of Lords.

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

From their immediate feedback to the facilitators, the young people involved in the project expressed very high levels of satisfaction with the WYRED process, as well as with the participation of their core group throughout each of the phases. As noted, at the conference where they presented their results, the audience gave their presentation a satisfaction level of “excellent” (90% of 62 respondents).

For some young people, the “buy in” to a methodology such as WYRED can represent a challenge for the facilitators. Young people may require a more directive form of facilitation from the outset in order to ensure that they are fully engaged and willing to self-organise. This may often be a result of spending many years within an education system that does not promote leadership skills and the meaningful active citizenship of young people within their schools. Therefore, when presented with a methodology that is based on “giving the keys of the car” to the young people, these young people are often afraid or reluctant to take on the role of driving the agenda.

However, within this group, there was no such reluctance. It is significant that this was a group, where there was already a nascent interest in being heard and sharing their experience. The obstacle that can be characterized as “the blank page problem” was largely absent. According to a facilitator “the WYRED process worked as a useful framework for them to work within”. The methodology supported them to become more motivated to maintain their involvement within the group.

It is relevant to mention that for this group the notion of the digital society was very much in the background. The group recognised the influence of social media, for example, on their lives and stress levels, but saw it as simply part of the context, as opposed to an issue in itself.

3.2 Case Study- Doga- Democracy in Schools

PROFILE OF DOGA

Doğa Schools is a large chain of private schools, with 104 campuses all over Turkey, with 7,500 members of staff, looking after 75,000 students. The teaching staff and the management teams are actively engaged in developing and implementing innovative teaching concepts. Among these concepts, two are of major importance for the pupil's development: **Natural Learning Concept (NLC)** is a primary school education model based on applied farming and training in a natural setting, focusing more on practice than theory. **MBA for teenagers (t-MBA)** is an international education model engaging high school pupils of Doğa Schools and other participating schools from around the world. The vision of the t-MBA Model is to create a platform for teachers, students, professionals, parents and anyone interested in t-MBA to share ideas, projects, and to widen their global knowledge.

Within WYRED, our methodology is being applied and tested within Doğa Schools in Istanbul. The range of children and young people involved in these projects are aged from 5 and upwards to 18 across the school community. This case study focuses on high school students and how they examined the theme of digital activism, specifically democracy within their schools.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

A single social dialogue workshop brought ten high school students together for a half day. In relation to the preparation for this session, a teacher described the process:

“We started by planning a social dialogue, and sent a mail inviting High School students from all Istanbul campuses of Doğa Schools and from Çamlica Religious High School. Out of the overwhelming response, we selected 10 students who proved most eager to take part. “

The social dialogue was structured as a workshop, held during school time on a school campus. The session described the 13 main themes stemming that had emerged from previous work within WYRED including such as environmental issues, self-image and self-confidence within digital society, using social media and Internet security and privacy. Moderation of the workshop was kept to a minimum by the facilitators as the participating students were capable of moderating themselves.

The procedure allowed for the exploring of the main themes, and from there to “dig into deeper details to end up with some project ideas related to the themes”. The workshop structure allowed for students to spend their time in conversation, as opposed to listening and observing. A teacher describes how this was applied.

“For example, we split them in teams, and they analysed the themes by brainstorming, by illustrating their ideas on flip charts, by writing key terms on post it notes, etc. The information was then shared with all other participants, taking turns and igniting constructive and interesting debates.”

The young people chose to focus their discussions on the theme of tolerance towards different cultures and opinions. When examining aspects of democracy in their daily lives, e.g. democracy and the Internet, democracy at work and democracy in school. A teacher described how the engagement of the young people was sustained.

“It turned out to be a very interactive session, which lasted just over 4 hours. We found that by providing a minimum of structure and guidance, students were not only very eager, but also very capable of sharing a stage to discuss themes very close to their hearts. In terms of structure and guidance, we provided a venue and a time window, and we explained the themes and the procedure we wanted to follow.”

The focal point for the follow up work became the idea and nature of democracy within their school. Two of these students took on to develop this as their WYRED project. The young people were supported in developing their understanding of how to proceed and potential outcomes, though reviewing a selection of completed projects on the WYRED platform.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Out of the theme relating to Democracy, as emerging from the workshop, the following initial research questions were posed:

1. How can young people reach a greater autonomy of decision making, especially in areas that affect their immediate and long-term future?
2. What are the responsibilities that young people need to take on if they are to reach a greater level of autonomy?
3. How can we ensure that the basic rights of children and young people are not curtailed at the same time?

With the assistance of the Activity Toolkit, the facilitators and teachers could point the participating students to a dedicated research methodology. This development work assisted in the further refinement of their research question to “How democratic is our school?”

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

The project aims were set out to find out about the nature and presence of democratic structures (such as student councils) within their schools, whether they are working actively and what students think about these types of structures. In order to collect this feedback, they designed a methodology focused on face to face interviews with a panel of 7 high school students, all aged 17 years.

The interviews focused on a discussion regarding the democratic nature of their school and how democracy was applied. These interviews were recorded and edited in order to be used as a documentary feature within the project. Some 7 key questions were asked:

1. Does your school have strict rules that restrict you?
2. If yes, what are the restricting rules? Do you think these rules are essential?
3. Do you believe that your school has a democratic system?
4. Do you have a student council? Is it active? Have you voted?
5. If schools weren't democratic, what kind of problems would the students face?
6. If students could choose their principals by voting, would that make schools more efficient?
7. Can you give examples to democratic changes which might impact the efficiency of students? How can you bring these changes to life?

The project members then analysed all feedback and created a dataset. Some key findings include:

- 2 out of the 7 students think that their school is democratic; the other 5 think that their school is partially democratic, with democratic structures being present but not active.
- 2 out of the 7 students aren't aware of the student council's presence or activeness; 5 out of the 7 students have voted at the student council elections however 3 out of the 5 reported that these councils weren't active.
- All 7 out of the 7 students think that the lack of democracy in schools would make the school a chaotic, disturbing place and would have negative effects on their education and overall efficiency.
- 5 out of the 7 students think that choosing their principals by voting would make the school much more efficient.
- 4 out of the 7 students suggested that student councils at their schools should be more active and students should be encouraged to participate in voluntary activities; 2 out of the 7 had no suggestions and the other student suggested that lessons should be shorter.

A detailed report was written to explain further about the research process and results. The video provides a visual support and insight into the data collection and interviewing process.

Teachers and facilitators were asked to examine the key factors that allowed the young people to apply the methodology and take research questions and turn them into projects. Here, it the teaching and learning culture within the Doga schools were considered critical in that the promotion of concepts of inquisitive and experiential learning ensures a strength of curiosity among learners. "Students are used to project work, and are empowered to ask and research questions, either on their own or with support from peers and staff. Based on this, it was a natural progression for students to turn their research into projects". The success of their approach and planning work enabled students from another High School to get involved in the structured research project.

Throughout each phase of the work, facilitation was kept to a minimum as participating students mainly drove the process themselves. Facilitators placed strong value on the use of the activity toolkit to act as a guide as well as the WYRED platform so that the students could learn from earlier projects and then share their own results.

These results included two reports on the process and results in Turkish as well as a full report in English and a video of the process that uses both English and Turkish. ¹

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

The final phase of the WYRED methodology involves producing a synthesis of the learning achieved within the project definition and delivery phases. An evaluation toolkit is available to facilitators and teachers.

The facilitator described their overall approach:

“We approached the phases with a formative evaluation mindset, i.e. sessions and procedures were evaluated as they happened, via direct input and questions and answers, both from moderators and from participating students. We did not carry out any formal, written summative evaluation.”

The most important learning points were considered to the following key aspects of the project cycle:

Ensure that the selection process is effectively organised. “In our case, we were not able to accommodate all interested students, so we had to make a selection; we were adamant not to make the selection based on academic grades, but on their willingness to be pro-actively involved in WYRED.” The project facilitators and teachers were aware that this methodological approach may not suit all learners, and therefore adapted as necessary during the planning phase.

A second important learning point was the importance to be a ‘guide by the side’, in other words “provide a solid but minimal framework for participant students to work in; let them take the lead and wait for them to ask for support, even when they seem to have hit a wall as young people have enough imagination and drive to find solutions for themselves; this also helps them to develop resilience”.

The third key insight that was gathered through the evaluation work of the team was connected to the element of dissemination channels. The planning and implementation of the project was based on the idea that the audience for the work would be beyond their peers and the student body. The participants summarised this lesson as the importance of “providing air time for the projects”. “Whatever the outcome; we found that participant students were self-motivated to explore themes close to their heart, but their motivation increased exponentially by knowing that their results were going to be given consideration by ‘the establishment’ (e.g. school leaders, local papers, etc.).”

¹ <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/democracy-schools>
<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/%C3%A7ocuk-haklarina-yolculuk>
<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/toplumun-sosyal-devlet-anlayi%C5%9Fina-ili%C5%9Fkin-tanimi>

Furthermore, the students submitted their project for a national competition held by Turkey's Research Council (TÜBİTAK). The knowledge that the project was going to be reviewed by the Research Council increased the students' motivation to do well. This national competition was considered to provide "additional air time".

3.3 Case Study- Early Years Organisation- “Children Examining “Fake” News”

PROFILE OF EARLY YEARS ORGANISATION

Early Years Organisation is the largest organisation in Northern Ireland working in the area of early years care and education for children aged 0-12 and their families. It was established in 1965, and over 50 years has been working to promote and develop high quality, evidence-informed early childhood services for young children, their families and communities. The vision of the Organisation is that young children are: strong, competent and visible in their communities; eager and able to learn; physically and emotionally healthy; respectful of difference. To deliver this vision, a range of key services and programmes are provided, including training for staff, parents and those working with children and projects in the areas of family health and learning.

Within WYRED, our methodology is being applied and tested within EY partner schools in Omagh. The range of children involved in these projects is aged from 7 to 11 years of age. This case study focuses on primary school students and how they examined the theme of access to reliable information, specifically how people find out if fake news is true or false.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

A series of 4 social dialogue workshops were carried out with 24 primary school students aged from 9 to 10 years. An important element of ensuring the engagement of this group of children is that the sessions were participative, fun and interactive. The experienced facilitators structured these sessions around included getting to know each other exercises that served to build relationships and provide a relaxed and supportive environment that would nurture open discussion.

One of the facilitators described this work: “At the beginning we acknowledged and listened to the children’s hopes and fears and regularly revisited these. The social dialogue sessions were structured in a format with setting/recapping on group contract, an ice breaker and then a focus on the topic/discussion of the social dialogue and then a brief “what did we learn” at the end. What worked best with the children was using ice breakers, games to introduce the social dialogue steps and also to reinforce and explore themes around the online world.

The additional use of resources such as video and selected websites allowed informal discussions that allowed for ongoing participation and interaction. The children were divided into smaller discussion groups in order to in keep their focus. The work of the smaller groups would then be shared with the wider group. One session that examined the area of digital values “worked particularly well as we discussed everyone’s moral compass and ethics around digital society and this invoked some great discussion that fed directly into the research phase.”

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Throughout the social dialogue sessions, the children were fully engaged and interested in the topics under discussion. As these sessions continued, the children were supported to explore more deeply areas relating to the digital world and how these themes affected their lives. As they became more inquisitive, looking to seek out more information, they began to focus on developing questions that they could explore further.

“As facilitators of the group we developed an understanding and got to know the children well. Considering their stage of development and having experienced what engaged them through the social dialogues we used creative methodologies to facilitate the transition from broader themes to a research question. The fact that the children already had a range of questions that came up as part of the social dialogue phase made defining the research question not that challenging.”

The children were supported in this manner through mind mapping exercises using a flip chart to help review and pinpoint a question.

“We were asking the children what they want to know about this question. So this helped them pinpoint exactly what they wanted to ask to get meaningful results.”

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

In relation to the development of the project, the facilitators were constrained in relation to the amount of time that they had with the children. “We met as a group on a weekly basis for about 1.5 – 2 hours with this group of

24 children. We had 4 social dialogue sessions, 8 research sessions where the children worked in groups exploring their questions and worked also on their own for one session without the facilitators. The 9th session was a dissemination event in front of their classmates, teachers and parents.”

The children demonstrated a keen interest in finding out more about the subject of fake news and how to determine the veracity of news content in general. They structured the research process across two groups. One group of 7 children decided to collate a survey made up of examples of fake news to see how many people could tell the difference. They collected responses from 230 people and analysed the resulting data to create a poster showing the results. Out of the 5 questions on the survey, the respondents recognised the fake story on 3 occasions. They were only wrong once. According to the analysis from the children, “this tells us that most people can tell the difference between real and fake news. Sometimes people share fake news by mistake because they believe it.”

The other group decided to develop a roleplay around fake news and wrote a powerpoint outlining the story. It was about a boy who set up a fake website and received lots of views. However he was caught by his father and his online world came to an end!

Throughout the research process, videos were captured of the children at work and performing the roleplay. However as these children are aged 10 or 11 years, it is not appropriate that these are available online for the

general public². A series of documents are available within the WYRED platform³, documenting the process of developing these two outputs. The unique powerpoint story developed by the children for the roleplay is available.

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

The final phase of the WYRED methodology involves producing a synthesis of the learning achieved within the project definition and delivery phases. An evaluation toolkit is available to facilitators and teachers. The facilitators made use of the evaluation template for the WYRED project with the children. While many facets of the toolkit were considered challenging in working with a younger cohort of children, the children were guided through the evaluation process and they used the template to present some insights on their experiences and perception of their engagement within the WYRED project. Feedback collected from the children throughout the phases highlighted the following key lessons:

1. The selection and use of appropriate games and ice breakers allowed the children and facilitators to get to know each other.
2. Children enjoyed group work and being able to carry out their own research. They loved the idea of getting on the platform and meeting other children from other countries, so the international dimension was a big attraction.
3. Having the same children over a length of time, building relationships and trust allowed for open and honest discussion that was not rushed and allowed for meaningful research to be carried out.
4. Elements within the evaluation toolkit allowed for some insights to be gained, but templates should be better tailored and more focused on the needs of children.
5. The experience of registering within the WYRED platform created excitement within the group. The children would benefit from regular access to similiarly aged groups of children in other countries, as well as content that is focused on themes of interest.
6. The planning of a research project should be linked within the practical aspects of the school academic year. A closer overlap with this timing ensures greater access to the children.
7. A greater focus on an active dissemination phase within WYRED would give the children a greater reward for all their efforts. "Research projects and artefacts need to be shared."

Central to the success of the project work with the children was the skills of the facilitators to be able to build strong relationships with their partners within the school and especially with the children themselves. This allowed for strong engagement and "getting meaningful dialogues and research projects".

The children were able to go through a research process, defining the questions, carrying out research, data collection, evaluation and recommendations. Both the children and the schools engaged placed a strong value

² EY continues to work with the technical partner within WYRED to examine ways of uploading the videos to the WYRED Platform only for view by the community users.

³ <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/fake-news-true-or-false>

on this work in developing competences associated with critical thinking and investigation. The children especially enjoyed talking about their research within the wider school community.

3.4 Case Study- MOVES- “Reflections on My Life”

PROFILE OF MOVES

MOVES has a specific research interest in examining fields of gender and diversity, with the aim of promoting equality at an individual, organisational, and on a societal level. MOVES is involved in the design and implementation of research projects within national and international spaces, especially in the areas of information technology, new media, equality strategies, and education. As a small private research organisation, MOVES works carefully and strategically to deliver innovative research and practice solutions, based on an active participation by MOVES team members in the research processes.

MOVES has expert knowledge in supporting research institutions, across a wide range of academic and scientific disciplines, in ensuring the practical and meaningful inclusion of all aspects of gender and diversity within their research projects. In 2016, it was awarded the Comenius EduMedia Seal for outstanding educational media in gender and IT.

Within WYRED, the MOVES team are working in close collaboration with educational establishments in Vienna and have taken a proactive role in engaging with young people who are dealing with educational and economic disadvantage. This case study focuses on a specific project, where one young person was supported and empowered through the WYRED methodology to use a creative approach to articulating herself and her future vision.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

A series of three social dialogue workshops were held within the group of young people. The facilitator carried out some introductory informal exercises where the group became familiarised with each other and the process to be followed. The WYRED project was presented and the themes were set out as per the early research work carried out within the project. From this point, the young people worked in smaller groups to define their areas of interest. The topics were summarised in a chart and the young people undertook a poll to select the five most appealing themes to be further developed through the research phases.

The focus of this case study turns to one of these responses. The facilitators felt that the manner in which the young person in question engaged with the process is of significant value and is worthy of closer inspection. The 16 year old was working towards an apprenticeship in this school. The school itself caters specifically for early school leavers or students who did not succeed within the mainstream system. Within the social dialogue phase, one of the facilitators highlighted that she seemed to require a lot of individual attention from the facilitators.

“It was very hard to get her attention; she seemed to be shy, sometimes even a bit hostile, when being asked for her preferences in regard to the topics. She always decided very quickly, one time for bullying,

the other time for future work and at the next meeting for environmental issues. She never joined a group, always worked alone.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In working with this young person, the facilitators provided support in examining the research topics and assisting in settling on a particular focus. The facilitators described that the young person displayed a keen interest in this aspect of the project cycle. This was attributed to the trust and confidence building work carried out in the social dialogue phase. The definition of the research question was seen as a relatively straightforward task, once the topic had been decided.

One educator highlighted that “as facilitators, we just should take care, that the question neither should be too broad nor too narrow, the first not to be lost within different aspects of a theme and the second not to hinder the research phase by not finding relevant resources.”

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

The young person decided to develop five separate research projects, with the support of her teachers and facilitators. As she was encouraged to express herself and find her own voice, she developed a strong creative flow. The WYRED platform became an important online space where this young student could share her writing and her ideas. One of the facilitators described how the research phase was a transformative experience.

“It seems that this student had had her hidden agenda within the dialogues as she took up all her topics also in the research phase and summarized them in her own thread on the platform. As soon as she got a Laptop in the research phase and was invited to write, she got kind of unstoppable and produced one poem, text essay, list, after the other. She mainly produced these artefacts out of herself, if it is needed to be labelled the term would be introspection. She put her artefacts on the platform and felt very proud of her achievements. “

The facilitators and teachers used their expertise and knowledge of the methodological approach to adapt this phase and link it directly to the capacities of the children and young people. Through such a flexible framework, the skills, capacities and competences of the particular groups of young people could be recognised and the phases adapted to meet their needs.

Again a facilitator describes how this approach was applied in practice:

“This means, that I proposed creative methods to the participants of this school (artefacts, paintings, collages, poems, short texts, discussions) whereas the other group being high level secondary II students (17-18 years), I informed about literature research, qualitative and quantitative research methodology and analyses.”

A more creative approach to expression and reflection allowed the young person here to present her thoughts about her life and society. One of her poems reflects on environmental concerns.

DAS LEBEN DES MÜLLS

Es Gibt viele Menschen die die Umwelt verschmutzen
Das meist gesehene sind übrige Zigaretten
Doch auch Plastik Müll wird häufig gesehen
Plastik wird auch im Meer gesehen, dadurch Menschen nicht sorgsam
mit dem Müll umgehen können
Doch Man sollte mehr auf die Umwelt schauen
denn es schadet auch den Tieren weil sie sich
in der Umwelt aufhalten
Mülltrennung wäre genauso wichtig, doch man sollte
wertschätzen wenn es nicht
in die Umwelt landet sondert dort wo es wirklich hingehört
Doch dieses Problem Gibt es heutzutage
fast nur noch bei den Jugendlichen
Es gibt Menschen die als Job Müll der anderen Entsorgen
Wir danken denn Menschen die das machen Sonst
Wäre unser Land nicht mehr schön
Doch sie werden nicht überall den Müll entsorgen
Doch schön wenn wir die Umwelt rein halten könnten

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

The facilitators and teachers reviewed and evaluated the work within this school. Each phase was analysed and a key factor in the successful implementation of this project was considered to be flexibility in the approach to working with young people. The young people were given a space to reflect on issues affecting their lives and then they were supported in examining these issues in more detail through critical thinking, research and expression. Positive outcomes were clear. One facilitator highlighted how the process had affected the young student.

“I think that this student was really empowered by WYRED. I suppose that when writing her text on the computer, the spelling correction of the text-programme helped her a lot to present her ideas, wishes and suggestions. When she had finished, she showed her artefact to me, asked me to do the last corrections and then she herself published it on her thread in the Eggenburg-Community. For me this

is the most valuable project I facilitated in WYRED, because I saw her growing in WYRED, she reflected on herself and her life and got taller with every new research meeting we had.”

A further key driver for this success is connected to the supportive atmosphere within the research process. Once provided with access to the laptop, this young student was enabled to move “to the other side of digitalisation”. She was no longer on the wrong side of a digital divide and could freely express her thoughts about her future.

3.5 Case Study- Oxfam Italy- “Responding to Globalisation and Self-Representation in the Digital Society”

PROFILE OF OXFAM ITALY

Oxfam Italia is part of an international confederation of 19 organizations that specialise in humanitarian aid and development projects, working together with partners and local communities in more than 90 countries. Oxfam works to mobilise the power of people to find practical, innovative ways for people to lift themselves out of poverty and thrive. Oxfam operates in crisis management situations to save lives and help rebuild livelihoods. As an organisation, it campaigns so that the voices of the poor influence the local and global decisions that affect them. Oxfam engages in partnership work with local organizations to support vulnerable women and men to end the injustices that cause poverty.

Within WYRED, the Oxfam team are working within second and third level schools and universities. This particular project brought together some 17 third level students aged between 21 and 23 years.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

The social dialogue sessions were designed to inspire young people to critically think about different issues affecting them in their online lives as well as regarding Italian society. The focus of these sessions examined the key themes for the young people of the implications of globalisation and also how young people represent themselves online. As the students moved onto later phases of the WYRED methodology, they used the learning from these sessions as a means of further exploring more specific themes of interest to them, such as the impacts of hate speech against migrants online and in society.

Among the issues identified for their first session, participants decided to discuss the issue of **globalisation** as an important transversal issue that impacts on a wide range of issues. Globalisation was perceived by the group as the extension of international borders that both narrows distances leading to new relationships among peoples, but also the same time it fosters migrations which can cause racism and integration issues. Globalisation was also regarded as a social phenomenon that promotes exchanges among cultures.

The young people used the social dialogue sessions to highlight the lack of connection that they feel with their local community. According to a facilitator the students had noted that

“Through social media they can interact at a different level, causing a lack of attachment and participation in their neighbourhoods. They recognise that this means that they are losing their cultural bonds and that this trend impacts at youth level in two ways: either rejecting globalisation embracing

nationalistic movements, which are led by “ignorance” and “differences in thinking and seeing the world”, or in homologation, same music, same shops, same fashion styles anywhere.”

During the conversation about Globalisation the trainer proposed an activity “to shake a bit the Eurocentric natural perspective” of the group. The activity is called “Our group is 100%” and the group was invited to divide in percentages subgroups according to the distribution of the world population, the distribution of wealth in the world and finally the distribution of hunger in the world (people living with less than 1,25 € per day).

According to one of the facilitators, “Despite the fact that the group were third level students of political science, the conversation was quite animated and the decision progress implied a lot of discussion. At the end of the activity the group returned to the flip-chart and shared that visualising how statistics represent real people, now they have a different level of awareness on globalisation’s impacts.”

The social dialogue sessions also allowed for discussions about “**self-representation**” with interesting insights emerging. In general, the group shared that self-representation is connected with how you project yourself on social media, “where you have to show the best of your life and all the successes, because everyone looks at

what you share without going deeper, this conditions the feelings and thoughts you can expose to the others and creating homologation in the type of experiences young people represent.”

In the same time, self-representation was also seen as “an opportunity to express yourself through blogs and social media, causing sometimes disinformation on relevant issues. It is difficult to distinguish between real and virtual life.”

Young people admitted within the session that they have “fear and difficulties in exposing themselves in person taking the challenge of sharing fragilities and every day difficulties, because it costs efforts and also because they are conditioned by social models.” For this reason, some of the group shared that they usually try to be assertive with other people when online. Some also felt that “social media friends can have a judging attitude towards others”.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The social dialogue sessions allowed for a stimulating discussion within these two thematic areas. The young people were again facilitated to take these discussions further and the participants began to examine how they would like to focus their research work. These sessions allowed for 17 young people from the third level institutes to decide on 15 specific projects. Based on the work within the social dialogues, every student “now defined a research question according to his/her personal life experience”. The following projects were chosen as part of the WYRED process.

1. Sociability and social media: help or condemnation?
2. Youth and communication: University radio case study"
3. Emotional impact of bullying and cyber bullying on young people.
4. Power & Dominion of social media
5. What originates stress in young people?

6. How do institutions support schools against cyber bullying?
7. How have the digital era and the economic crisis revolutionised the relationship between youth and labour market?
8. Citizens' social and electoral participation
9. How does fear for future employment opportunities influences our present reality?
10. Youth and political participation
11. What does democracy mean?
12. Globalisation. ONG's denounce and photographic evidence
13. A new generation!: Integration of young migrants in school
14. How is Italy seen by other countries?
15. What has changed over the last 10 years, if it has changed, in the perception of people of different cultures?

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

The facilitators worked closely with the young people to assist in taking these research questions and themes and focusing on different research methods that would allow the young people to answer questions and test assumptions. A wide range of methods were made available, including creative or journalistic approaches, as well as action research methods or ethnographic research tools. Many of the students opted for qualitative research techniques using interviews and face to face application of questionnaires. More quantitative approaches were also involved, including online surveys and database analysis.

Among the research projects, one student set out to investigate among her schoolmates with migrant backgrounds, how they played a role as intercultural mediators between the family and the outer society. She used workshops and creative approaches to work with her peers, as well as carrying out research through organising social dialogues at school. She asked policy makers to “give new generations a chance to spread initiatives of this kind, in order to contribute, even with small steps, to a big and radical change.”

Another project set out to understand how Italy and Italians are seen by people from other countries; “if usual stereotypes - regarding what people throughout the world think about Italian culture - are reliable or not, and what first comes to foreigners' mind when they think about Italy”.

The main finding was that “Italians are seen always happy and having a good quality of life, but when tourists come to Italy often change their ideas due to all the things that don’t work properly.”

When you, somehow, get information about Italy, what do they concern?

56 risposte

Italian way of life is seen as particularly joyful and Italian products have a worldwide reputation of high quality. The research stresses the importance of highlighting all the work behind “made in Italy” products. This might involve campaigns to highlight the technical and academic excellence in fields of technology or science. Such a campaign “could contribute to dispel the myth that Italians have good products which they can’t export appropriately”. The researcher carried out his research using an online survey and interviews both qualitative and quantitative. The results were then interpreted and discussed through an article and a video.

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

Across these 15 projects, carried out by 17 young people, more than 300 young people were engaged through these research approaches, whether through interviews or being participants within surveys. The young people also were supported to produce “30 seconds pitch videos of all the researches for viral dissemination on social media”.

The young people were furthermore engaged within a WYRED showcase workshop within the premises of Roma Tre University, where all the researchers had the opportunity to discuss with decision and opinion makers about their findings and recommendations.

According to the facilitators, the sessions with the young people went well. “Some of the participants were comfortable with non-formal settings, for others it was a new experience, but all of them actively contributed to the development of the session bringing their personal experiences and perspectives both on social issues and their lifestyles.”

OIT included among the topics of discussion globalisation and the Agenda 2030 as most of the participants were not aware of this international legal framework. It was an important step to engage YP in the research phase and motivate them to further explore the issues presented into the social dialogues. The work within the WYRED methodology can be delivered more effectively when the activities were more defined and the young people had a clearer idea of what was expected from them. Furthermore, the team from the University of Roma Tre supported the students once they could recognise the inherent value of their research projects. This was exemplified in the University providing the students with the space to discuss their findings and recommendations in a public event.

3.6 Case Study- Partners for Youth Empowerment- “Housing and homelessness within our community”

PROFILE OF PARTNERS FOR YOUTH EMPOWERMENT (PYE)

PYE is an international organisation that works with teachers, youth workers, and other leaders to empower young people within their communities. PYE’s mission is “to unleash the power, purpose, and potential of young people worldwide”. PYE works with local partners, in each country where it has a base, to build the creative capacity of young people. Based on its “”, PYE offers facilitation training directly to the people who teach, mentor and support youth. This allows the young people to received support and training in life skills and confidence building to meet their challenges of school, work and their digital world.

In 2016, PYE together with 34 partners trained over 4,100 practitioners in 14 countries. As a result, 238,000 youth were impacted through the Creative Community Model methodology. Some 2,100 young people were also reached through camps that used the same model. PYE has also developed an online International Learning Network of over 15,000 practitioners, where facilitators connect, share and learn about youth empowerment.

Within WYRED, PYE is working with young people through second level schools and youth spaces in London, Brighton and other parts of the UK. This case study is based on a piece of work carried out with some 8 young people in Brighton, aged from 14 to 15 years and specifically how one young person was inspired by the WYRED methodology to explore issues relating to homelessness in his community.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

The Brighton school works with children and young people who have struggled with school to overcome their barriers to learning. The school’s vision is to re-build the pupils self-belief by teaching them skills to success for lifelong learning. At the school, the students are taught in small groups and may also get one-to-one support for some specific area of work. The school works closely with other organisations and teams who may be working with pupils, including local Child and Adolescent Mental Health Services and Learning Disability Teams. The students who attend include children with special educational needs, as well as those who have significant gaps in their learning or who have been excluded from mainstream schools.

Pupils often have special needs such as speech and language difficulties, learning difficulties, autistic spectrum conditions, ADHD, Tourette’s syndrome, oppositional defiant disorder, or occasionally hearing, visual or medical issues.

For the facilitator, this was the first time to work with the Year 10s who were aged 14-15. As they were a relatively new group, they were still getting to know each and there were still some trust issues among the group.

The facilitator was aware that many of the young people had been expelled from other mainstream schools. For this reason, as part of the social dialogue phase, specific efforts were made to ensure that the young people were able to access sufficient encouragement to participate and offer their opinions in constructive ways. As per one of the teachers: "They all have valid opinions and ideas and are able to participate given the right circumstances."

The lead facilitator describes the challenges in getting the social dialogue session up and running:

"I began the session with a brief introduction of the project then played an 'ice-breaker' which helped to engage the group and helped me to gauge the mood. One young person found it difficult and even said; "I'm not standing up and speaking in front of everyone". We watched the short animation 'The Innovation of Loneliness' on vimeo. This helped to start some discussion. We spoke about use of social media. It was put forward that there are too many options available. Most of them are too 'long', meaning boring. One young man asked 'Why is social media considered a threat?' which led to a debate about cyber bullying and to not get too affected by what others say about you online. We also spoke about the use of money and how none of the young people present had bank accounts which made cashless payments obsolete."

The icebreakers worked well to create a sense of trust and encouraged participation, allowing for everyone's voice to be heard. The techniques that were most useful for the social dialogue session were mind mapping exercises, allowing for the visualisation of the issues. The use of the online videos also promoted their engagement with the WYRED themes and allowed for creative ways to tell stories and further engage with the project.

In order to get the group talking about the subject, the facilitator followed their own interests. They could then take charge of the conversation and direction of the discussion, ensuring that they were supported to talk about issues that affected them in their lives. Giving the group activities was also found to work better than allowing too much free discussion as they wanted to talk about other topics e.g. the state of the schooling system and money of the lack of it.

A key helping factor at this stage of the project was the support of the school and their teachers. They encouraged the creativity of the young people to remain engaged with the project.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Further sessions focused on discussion of issues they care about. The facilitator supported this process using creative activities. This ensured that an initial reluctance to engage in discussion was replaced by an animated session, where many topics emerged and strong opinions were expressed. The session then allowed the young

people to work in small groups to allow more focus on research questions, such as in relation to the pros and cons of school uniforms and the difficulties and importance of their youth voice being heard and ways to communicate to those in power.

The following research themes were explored by the young people through this phase:

- 1) Climate change and its impact on the cost of living for young people
- 2) Education and school uniforms.
- 3) The power of “Youth Voice”
- 4) Online platforms- access and permissions
- 5) School hours and attendance
- 6) Cyber bullying and especially in relation to people using multiple accounts to pester others.

In examining how they would develop these themes into specific research projects and questions, the young people adopted differing approaches, with some keen to focus on research topics with a social dimension including the impacts of racism and poverty in Brighton on issues of homelessness and drug addiction. Others were more interested to focus on concerns associated with the digital society.

Through this phase, they were supported to examine how to find reliable information sources within the community and school. Working in the smaller groups had allowed quieter voices to be heard and for greater clarity to be provided to questions.

One young person decided to take a specific theme associated with accessing information and apply it in relation to about the opportunities available for young people regarding housing and homelessness. It had been noted within the group discussion that there had been a sharp increase in homelessness in Brighton over the previous 12 months (up from 78 to 144 rough sleepers).

In examining the types of research methods that they might use in their projects, a session was used to look at the WYRED platform and review the projects that were available there. The young people got a clear sense as to how to get on the platform and take their research out into the public. They also were inspired to examine and use creative means to carry out the research and then to disseminate their findings, such as photography and film and graphic design.

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

The facilitator and teachers were able to offer support to the young people as they designed their projects. The use of a participatory exercise called a ‘problem tree’ was used to develop further understanding of how to approach their research topics, including in one instance an examination of the causes and effects of poverty in their community. This process helped the young people to generate deeper thinking, using this visualisation method, about the root causes of the issue and their expressions as branches.

For the young person focusing on the issue of housing and homeless, the group watched a video created by Brighton Council illustrating how homelessness can be just one month away for some families due to redundancy and other factors.

The follow up discussions were prompted by the project in question as to “why we should care about the predicament of others”. The teachers were impressed with this work and were keen to develop a sense of empathy among the students.

The project on homelessness was framed as the production of a short documentary about the situation. The young person was also interested in interviewing some different people related to the issue. The project began with an examination of statistics on homelessness in Brighton. The findings were shared with the group and the young people were surprised to discover that numbers had doubled in the 12 months previous and is the second largest population after Westminster.

The project further researched the cost of housing, both buying and renting in Brighton. The young person looked at estate agents, forums and listings and found statistics online about the average cost of living and the average wage in Brighton. These findings were again shared with the wider group and people were surprised to find out the average wage is below the average cost of living.

The project looked into how much it would cost this young person to get his own 1-bedroom flat when he leaves home. In order to present this visually, the young person made a cardboard cut-out house and was assisted by the facilitator to make the short film with his findings.

According to the facilitator, the research process was a personal experience for the young person:

“He told me he had asked his mum how much council tax she paid and how often she had to pay her bills. I was pleased to hear that he had been thinking about these issues, was talking about it at home and had started to gain a better understanding of his Mum’s responsibilities. We made price tags and tried to convey his findings in a creative way. It was in the moments crafting or setting up the camera and reviewing the shots that we were able to deepen our conversations. He had the chance to follow a train of thought and consider others than himself. We talked about homelessness and how Brighton seemed to have noticeably more people living rough on the streets. The research process was giving him empathy for those he saw on the streets who couldn’t find affordable housing or were dealing with other issues.”

In the process of making the film, the young person had sparked his imagination had become committed to completing his creative project in order to express what he had found out. Again the facilitator describes the success of the process:

“I think in this instance it was the opportunity to use his creativity to further explore an issue that allowed him to reflect and empathise with the people behind the statistics. Watching his film in front of his peers was also an empowering experience. To be witnessed expressing your voice gives it more power. I hope that participating in this WYRED process helped the students to think for themselves, follow their train of thought through a variety of mediums, find out facts and develop their belief in their ability to create, communicate and enjoy the research process.”

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

Through this final phase of presenting his work and his film to his peers and family, the young person explained how proud he was of the creative process and output and the research that he had carried out. The key factors that allowed this young person and his peers to maintain his engagement through the process were attributed as following:

- Smaller groups if not individual attention worked better than bigger groups.
- Interactive activities kept the interest and momentum going with this particular group of students
- A strong focus was placed on ensuring that the young people would feel an atmosphere of trust and safety in the room. Without this, the young people did not feel ready to express themselves.
- The importance of promoting creative skills and endeavour- the young person was interested and engaged in using his artistic creativity both by creating the cardboard house and making a film;
- Support and individual attention was crucial- the young person was engaged by the fact that an interested adult brought equipment, encouraged him, supported him, asked questions and took an interest in the creative process, the success of the work came about as a result of individual attention and support from facilitator and teachers;
- Ensuring that the final product can be shared and presented is very important- the young person was inspired to take the learning and discussions outside of the school and his peers by engaging with his family about these themes and issues.

3.7 Case Study- TAU- “How to shape a better future for the Israeli society”

PROFILE OF TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY (TAU)

Tel Aviv University (TAU) is Israel’s largest institution of higher learning, home to over 30,000 students studying in nine faculties and over 125 schools and departments. The students are spread across the spectrum of sciences, humanities and the arts. It is consistently ranked among the world’s top 100 universities, as well as the top 20 institutions in terms of scientific citations.

TAU participates in WYRED through the unit for Technology and Society Foresight (TSF) and through the School of Education. TSF (formerly ICTAF – the Interdisciplinary Centre for Technology Analysis and Forecasting) is a leader in technology foresight and policy-support research, assisting policy-makers to reach informed decisions based on technology’s role in society. The School of Education plays a key role in creating and nurturing knowledge relating to the education system, with approximately 200 researchers employed in its research system. Research carried out at the School of Education has won recognition from educational policy-makers in Israel and from international institutions.

Within WYRED, TAU researchers are actively involved with all the project tasks, and lead the Delphi activity. Specific effort focused on young people is carried out through the university’s Summer Youth University programmes. This case study examines a project that took place over four weeks, bringing together some 48 students aged from 16 to 17 years. Through an analysis of their position within Israeli society, they posed questions in such areas as gender, migration, environment, employment and digital society, addressing themes of tolerance, integration and self-image.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

The TAU Summer Youth University involves 50 high school students from Israel's geographic periphery, many of them from underprivileged groups. The majority of these young students were the first in their families to enrol in higher education courses.

They were brought together on the TAU campus and were facilitated to participate within the WYRED methodology. The participants were initially briefed on the project background and the thematic concerns. The social dialogue phase then asked the participants to think about their future society, and as representatives of the young generation, point out dilemmas and issues that they see facing them. They were working on the basis that they would research these issues in more depth, before structuring and presenting these as a challenge to decision-makers.

The WYRED programme began with a pre-prepared video clip (presented by imaginary student from the year 2030) with a pessimistic scenario of the future, which calls for action from young people today and urges them

to demand action from decision makers, in order to shape a better future. This inspired the subsequent discussions and projects.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The dialogue phase led directly into the definitional work as the participants learned more about various problems related to the Israeli society through tours and lectures on a variety of subjects, e.g. artificial intelligence, information society, economic gaps, inclusion, etc. This enabled the selection of research questions and topics. The young people were supported and facilitated to work in groups of 8-9 persons.

Six research themes were selected, all with a clear focus on future impacts and how policymakers could be challenged:

1. Gender and inclusion
2. Refugees and integration
3. Sustainability and the environment
4. Socio-economic gaps in Tel Aviv
5. Segregation and promoting understanding
6. Examining the four "Israeli tribes"

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

Each of the research themes was developed into a dedicated project using an adapted version of the "Futures Wheel" method (used for visualization of consequences of certain changes) as the primary resource. This tool was used during their special brainstorming sessions, and prompted them to create a visual representation of the themes and issues that they were researching.

One project focused on creating debate about gender and inclusion. The local context for the students was that a large scale protest was happening during the time of their participation in the project. Tens of thousands of men and women came to Tel Aviv's Rabin Square to support the LGBT community in their demands for equal surrogacy rights for gay men. The issue had become prominent in Israeli society, leading to a desire among the young students to talk about inclusion. The main themes of the discussion were concerned with how gender and inclusion "problems" will be affected by future social changes. Within this project, the students examined how to raise awareness of these themes through using TV and Internet series and content. Any campaign must "conquer the hearts of the people". Furthermore, the education system should have inclusion at its core. Through such steps, the young people considered that social stigmas can be challenged.

Another project allowed for students visit a particularly disadvantaged part of south Tel Aviv city. Through this visit, they learned about problems affecting the refugee' population as newcomers to the neighbourhood, and of the host population. Following this visit, the students were supported through the WYRED methodology to use the futures wheel method. This approach prompted discussion concerning developments that have allowed

for greater ease of population movement and new migration patterns. They asked questions about other push and pull factors such as how developments in communications may have led to increased awareness among populations about differences between societies. The futures wheel approach encouraged an analysis within their project regarding how these changes may continue to affect migration trends in the future and what this may mean for policy makers.

One of the research teams were inspired to examine issues relating to socioeconomic deprivation in Tel Aviv and research the implications of this socio-economic gap, including the role of technology. The picture below represents the results of the first brainstorming session where the students thought about different aspects of the problem like periphery vs centre, housing, gentrification, and poverty, and started to think about solutions – most of them were related to education.

A further research team were inspired by a research trip, in which they saw a variety of solutions both at the School of Environmental Studies at Tel Aviv University and on the roof of one of Tel Aviv's big shopping centres, two buildings that implement principles of sustainability. They also received input from academics working within environmental studies to examine themes regarding sustainable development. Of particular interest

within this project was their desire to look at how to save resources and promote recycling, green energy, public transportation and the use of virtual products. Another group believed that they should be a living example of peaceful coexistence between different religions and cultures - Arabs and Jews, religious and secular - bridging gaps and disagreements, studying and living together. They argued that young people from different backgrounds should meet each other (online and offline) and share their common interests in order to be more tolerant to people from different cultures. As a practical tool to promote this idea they designed a mobile app for connecting between teens based on their common hobbies and interests.

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

The WYRED methodological phases that were applied with the young people allowed for them to articulate their own vision for the future, and to examine how they and others should be responding to the pressing challenges as they identified them. There was scope for disagreement and discussion among the young people about the role of technology, namely the need to relate to technology when discussing the future of society.

One of the facilitators highlighted how the WYRED methodology had successfully encouraged open discussion and created a safe space for sharing of ideas.

“It was rather surprising that some young people did not want to discuss the role of technology in the future society – they felt that it diverted the discussion into a dead end. However, most of them have changed their mind about it along the process. Based on their experience in living/acting in the digital world, they claimed that social networks are catalysts for hate speech but can also be a promoter for social change. Therefore, some groups decided to use technological tools to promote their ideas. It was also quite surprising to find out that although some of them came from very conservative communities, they didn’t hesitate to discuss gender and LGBT issues.”

The background lectures and tours were regarded as very important in initiating the WYRED process and provide them the necessary knowledge in order to proceed. The facilitators felt that the young people were inspired by the lecturers and the tours.

“We believe that this is useful means to give them the chance "to dive into the problem". Furthermore, they lacked information about ways to influence the key decision makers, so lectures about social media, information society, journalism and lobbying were very important to their sense of competence and helped them to use media tools more efficiently.”

Applying a more creative approach to the support and direction of the students was considered to yield better outcomes:

“Work groups that were guided by a young junior instructor were very creative, and sometimes more dedicated to the project than those that were guided by a senior instructor. This may be an indication

that we need to give the students more opportunities to lead the process - in accordance with the real WYRED spirit.”

The “futures wheel” method, in a form adapted for the young people, was regarded as a useful resource and provided a workable framework and set of guidelines as a starting point in the research projects.

The young people explored problems that in their opinion would be important in the year 2030, and proposed creative solutions to be shared with large audiences and decision makers. The work was done in teams where they could express their opinion in moderated dialogues.

During the graduation ceremony of the Summer University they showcased their projects to a wide audience including senior representatives from the Israeli Ministry of Education, the third sector, and educators. A video was made and delivered by the students and shared on the WYRED platform.

During the presentation, the young students stood in front of a slide that says "Thank you" in a special font that combines letters in Hebrew and Arabic. The students indicated that they were fed up with traditional politics and "old" media, they were more interested in discussing the social perspective and looking to their future with a "feel of inventiveness"..

3.8 Case Study- USAL- “Globalisation, the nation and the individual in today's world”

PROFILE OF UNIVERSITY OF SALAMANCA (USAL)

The University of Salamanca was founded in 1218 and is one of the oldest Universities in Europe. Today it fosters a culture of every branch of teaching and has wide-ranging experience in international collaborations. It has cooperation agreements with over 300 institutions around the world and its researchers participate in international projects, in particular within European research frameworks and programmes. Since 2009, the University of Salamanca has been recognised as a Campus of International Excellence by the Spanish Government, as a result of its quality and experience in teaching, training, research activities and academic life.

USAL is participating in WYRED through the Research Group in InterAction and eLearning (GRIAL). The group includes a large number of researchers from different fields, with most members coming from a technical or a pedagogical background. GRIAL also has extensive expertise in e-Learning project management, the development of pedagogical methodologies and models and in wider the field of online learning.

Within WYRED, as well as acting as project lead and the partner responsible for the technical development of the WYRED platform, GRIAL has worked directly with students of USAL, as well as high school students in Salamanca, to test the methodology and develop a range of WYRED projects. These students of local high schools and USAL tend to be aged between 16 and 25 years. The focus of this case study is work carried out with a large group of high school students that resulted in the development of 36 projects based on the themes of “globalisation, the nation and the individual in today's world”.

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

A series of social dialogue workshops took place with the 92 high school students within their class groups. These lasted over a half day of school. Two school teachers were in charge of the workshop and then they monitored the next phases. The project group facilitated this session and then continued to link in with and monitor this initial phase with the young people.

All the 92 students involved are studying at the same High School “IES Venancio Blanco”. Two teachers from the school, involved in the teaching of philosophy and history, assisted in the coordination and facilitation of the research activity phases. The teachers engaged the students by presenting the WYRED mission and encouraging debate around the WYRED themes. The discussion led to the selection a broad theme in relation to globalisation and its meanings in relation to the young people. The adoption of this broad framework then allowed for the students to examine their interests and how they would work on their individual and group research projects.

During this initial phase, the students were supported by the project team and assigned mentors for the duration of the project work. This allowed them to structure the period of time available to them which was to be 20 to

60 hours of real work, during some school time, but mostly over their own spare-time (afternoons and weekends) for around three weeks over March and April 2018. This was the timeline during which the research activities would take place and final research outputs and artefacts would be produced and shared.

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research definition phase surfaced five specific questions that the students would address. The teachers worked with the students to encourage further discussion to allow for a deeper analysis and understanding of the theme “Globalisation, nation and individual in today's world”. They examined the historical and cultural background and the implications on their daily reality.

The students, organised in small groups, were free to focus their research on a specific event or topic within the themed framework. Topics that arose included wars, terrorism, social media and the feminist movement. They also were supported to identify the manner and means by which they would present the results of their work. These formats included using a short film, essays, drawings or animations.

The five research questions that the students honed in on were the following:

1. Gender stereotypes and discrimination: Does the digital society contribute to improving (or worsening) the perception of gender stereotypes and forms of discrimination based on sex, sexual orientation, and gender identity?
2. Necessary changes in education: To what extent can the digital society improve or worsen future education? What should change in education so that it adapts to the needs and interests of young people?
3. Social media: In what way do the technologies influence the personality or the formation of it?
4. Environment: Are we aware of the main environmental problems that affect our world, and that have affected us throughout history? To deal with it is responsibility of the new generations.
5. Society: How the evolution of the concept of society, the construction of identity and nationality, as well as the phenomenon of globalization could be topics for discussion to share with policy makers?

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

All students grouped themselves in relation to these five research questions. For the most part, they were in research teams of two or three young people. As they worked through their research planning, developing their specific methodologies and collection of data, a key factor was the strong engagement of the teachers as facilitators. As experts both in the topic under analysis and in teaching and learning methodologies, their profile and experience were critical for the students’ research activities, particularly at the beginning of the process.

This experience and support was considered important in ensuring that such a large group could work coherently and strategically together. One of the facilitators explained.

“The students felt very involved in the research experience, free to express their opinions and to choose the language and the tools to do it. After the first approach tutored by the teachers in the face to face session, they worked autonomously with excellent results.”

All the projects are available on the WYRED platform.⁴ One particular project was presented at the European Youth Event, hosted in June 2018 in the European Parliament in Strasbourg. This allowed for the WYRED participants to take this opportunity to share their story with other young Europeans and to make their voices heard. During the event, 9,000 participants discussed their ideas for the future of Europe with decision makers.

This WYRED project was called “The Face of Society”. It involved the production of a video that offers a reflection regarding “the effects of globalization, excessive consumption and technology in the creation of undifferentiated young people without their own identity, which reflect the face of society, and not their own”. The video was extremely well received by the audience of young people in Strasbourg.

The group documented their participation in the event and this was described in the WYRED platform.

#EU AND Vera, Manuel and Guillermo

06/06/2018 Blog , Newsletter

This weekend, on the 1st and 2nd of June, Vera, Manuel and Guillermo, accompanied by their teachers, had the opportunity to present their WYRED project at the European Youth Days held in the European Parliament of Strasbourg.

In their work, students through a short film analyze how social networks and the process of cultural globalization blur the personality of young people and make it difficult to build their own identity.

The three students selected have presented the results of their research in one of the events of these conferences and have also participated in one of the debates of the European Parliament on the challenges of the Digital Revolution with MEPs and members of various associations and educational centers throughout Europe. Europe.

The experience has meant an extraordinary training opportunity and a personal experience that develops fundamental competences of these future citizens.

Follow the debate on the [WYRED platform](#) !

⁴ <https://wyredproject.eu/category/research-projects/>

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

The final phase of the WYRED methodology involves producing a synthesis of the learning achieved within the project definition and delivery phases. An evaluation toolkit is available to facilitators and teachers.

From a delivery point of view, the teachers were very satisfied with the application of the WYRED methodology. The young people were supported to understand the nature of the research process and once they had developed a consensus regarding the overall themes, they worked independently within their groups to successfully complete the phases of the methodology.

The teachers indicated that they had no specific issues or problems in relaying the methodology to the students. They highlighted that the young people were keen to self-organise and take charge of their work, once they knew that the support was available if required. The teachers also pointed to the creative responses that the various groups used to present their results.

One of the facilitators indicated their high levels of satisfaction “concerning the quality of the products in terms of adjustment to the initial objective of the research and formal presentation, facilitators and young people analysed the final products and the level of satisfaction of the groups with respect to the results obtained.”

As noted above, one of the 36 projects within this WYRED methodological process was presented within an important international event for young people allowing for dissemination of the key messages from the project to policymakers as well as the opportunity for the students to gather feedback from their peers.

3.9 Case Study- YEU- “Brave New You”

PROFILE OF YOUTH FOR EXCHANGE AND UNDERSTANDING (YEU)

Youth for Exchange and Understanding was founded in Strasbourg in 1986 by a group of 120 young people from 11 different countries. In 1989 it was recognised as a member association of the European Coordination Bureau. Today YEU is a member of the European Youth Forum which is the independent platform for INGyOs and NYCs in Europe.

The organisation is made up of young people from over 30 countries from across Europe and Africa. YEU is run by young people for young people by means of a democratic structure and its members are mainly working on a voluntary basis. The limit age to participate in our activities is 30 years but the majority of participants are under the age of 25. It is young people who decide about activities of the organisation, define the strategies and implement the action plans, run the organization and ultimately evaluate it.

It is important to note that most young people in YEU are actively involved in other aspects of civil society, frequently establishing links between Member Organisations and local, regional and national institutions, other youth organisations and the community in general, extending the participation in the international organisation to the local dimension.

Within WYRED, YEU facilitators have brought the methodology within the set of organisational activities. For example, when young people are gathered together at international events, the methodology is used to support and encourage debate, discussion and focus. This case study examines a research project that was implemented with a group of 95 young people within a YEU programme that involved a wide range of national settings, where the research projects were facilitated. The programme took place over 12 months, with the focus of these projects extending to cover the full WYRED agenda:

- Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping
- Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security
- Living on social media, living with stress
- Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy
- Digital participation and activism, digital divide

PHASE 1: SOCIAL DIALOGUE WORK

The 95 young people involved were brought together through a YEU programme, called Brave New You. This programme included disparate international events such as youth exchanges, online campaigns, training courses, as well as the WYRED research activities. The vision behind the programme was “the promotion of a tolerant and open-minded society that perceives its differences as enriching power and distinctive advantage”.

Facilitators worked to develop capacities of young people and also youth workers. The programme also aimed to reach out to disadvantaged young people and tackle narratives that exclude them.

Not all of the 95 young people participated in the 11 social dialogue sessions. These were facilitated at different stages during the initial phase of the programme's 12 month period.

YEU facilitators carried out these social dialogue sessions both offline during YEU events, as well as online (using the WYRED platform). As members of the YEU network and their member organisations, the young people were familiar with the overall Brave New You programme and its key aims:

- To create counter narratives by getting to know other people, whose presence, existence and difference they may have been afraid of
- To develop capacities of youth leaders and practitioners in order to give them educational and practical tools, thus empowering them to reach out to young people of different backgrounds in their own communities.
- To showcase the power of quality youth work to change lives of young people and, subsequently, communities and societies they get actively engaged in.
- To promote intercultural and gender perspective in youth work as a cross-cutting/transversal issue.

The young participants engaged actively within the social dialogue phase. They were introduced to the WYRED methodology and it was made clear about how the methodological phases would be implemented through the "Brave New You" programme. There was clearly a good fit between the programme and the WYRED approach. One of the facilitators involved in one of the social dialogue sessions described the process:

"After the group bonded, the process was functioning based on their needs and thoughts and they were in the end facilitating the process themselves. The individual work, gave them safe space to express themselves and therefore develop their thought by the time they had to work as a group. At some point, they saw themselves as actual parts of society and were reflecting on their actions and expectations and therefore took "responsibility" of using the outcomes to start changing the status quo from them."

Coming from different backgrounds and as youth workers, the participants saw through this process a chance for them to take the tool back home in order to engage more young people. Through coming together and working together in this initial phase, the young people were relating the group work to their local realities, "it feels like we can actually talk and people will actually hear us and together work to change thanks to processes and projects like WYRED."

PHASE 2: DEFINING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The work of translating this social dialogue work of analysis and discussion into specific research questions was "realised according to young people interest and the current situation in their local communities". As they returned from the YEU events, where the young people had the opportunity to talk about the WYRED themes

and topics, the young people were supported to take their interests and frame the next steps in their research work.

The young people went on to develop the specific research questions, following the YEU events, in their local communities. A facilitator pointed out about the manner in which the Brave New You programme events had triggered the initial discussions. “The YEU events were the starting points of the discussion. After the YEU events the YP continued developing these questions using the WYRED platform as a tool and a meeting point.”

These 5 specific questions were developed:

1. How online narratives affect disadvantaged communities (Roma; Socioeconomic status; Refugees)
2. Cyberbullying and Online Hate Speech. What can be done to be protected and stop such cases?
3. Gender online? What are the local realities and how does that reflect online?
4. Conflicts and Bi-communal cooperation. Can Digital spaces and tools bring people together?
5. Homophobia online. Is there a solution to raise awareness and protect victims?

As each set of participants returned from the programme events to their own countries, they then selected one from those questions. They then developed a specific research project related to their local community and their personal interests.

PHASE 3: DELIVERING RESEARCH PROJECTS

Young people from each of the following 11 countries took part in research activities emerging from these five questions. The key factors that allowed the young people to turn research questions into projects were related to social, political and cultural priorities that faced them in their local communities.

1. Italy
2. Portugal
3. Greece
4. Azerbaijan
5. Cyprus
6. Serbia
7. Slovenia
8. Turkey
9. Kosovo
10. FYROM/Macedonia
11. Bosnia Herzegovina

The Italian research project involved young migrants and young refugees in the process. The young people developed a questionnaire as part of their research work in order to examine how social media and online platforms can affect the perceptions of immigrants. This led to the development of some tips and pointers to

help people in dealing with online activities to try to promote “a genuine and fruitful online discussion, where different community can enter in contact and know better each other.”

In Portugal, the young people were aged between 12 and 20 and also sought to examine this theme, specifically examining “how social media and online platforms can discourage hateful behaviour among youngsters living in different neighbourhoods?” Through the development of a questionnaire, the young people collected information in their neighbourhoods in relation to how their communities and especially their young people are represented on online sources. The analysis highlighted that:

“The narrative behind all the discriminatory messages, spread mostly through social medias, is based on socioeconomic stereotypes. The intention is to make neighbourhood people feel less worthy and lose their dignity. Most of the young people who collaborate to the questionnaire think that the increase use of digital devices for this purpose can encourage hateful behaviour and violent actions among young people.”

As a solution to these challenges and how they are represented, the young people developed a set of proposals including the importance of organising “more social and cultural activities from young people and their families. Bringing together people from different areas of the town is a fundamental step, so they can know each other and socialize in a safe environment. It will be important to guide some discussions in order to create an alternative ways to respond at all the verbal and online attacks that people constantly receive. In addition, there should be organized some activities promoting the respect of human rights and activities helping people to know each other so they can, by playing, break down some mental stereotypes. Then, in order to trying to prevent hateful speech around us it is essential to teach to young people how to use digital devices and online platforms as well as social medias, what should be published and how.”

The Serbian group of young people also took up this theme within their research project, when they sought to examine “how online sources and media can support the perspective of young people and support the integration of communities like Roma?” The project set out to examine how to change the mind of Serbian youths, fight against the stereotypes, with the aim of promoting the integration of Roma people within Serbian youth community through the use of mixed activities and online tools. The project investigated the means of providing the opportunity for online and offline interaction between young people from Roma and non-Roma backgrounds with the aim of challenging youth to take into consideration the obstacles and difficulties that Roma people can face. The project looked at how best to use the online world as a positive channel for information and communication, through the creation of a YouTube channel as a space for interviews and storytelling “about their dreams of future or how they can help to change their role in the Serbian society”.

foto: Katarina Agbaba

A further channel that was explored within the project was related to the promotion of online activism, “where in order to answer to all the discriminatory videos and pictures published online against Roma people, it could be useful to create an online campaigns is fighting against fake news in websites which usually write about the problems that Roma people generate to the Serbian community. Through the online campaign will be spread only correct and official information that will make Serbian people aware of the real situation and will give the opportunity to Roma young people to speak and be heard by the society.”

PHASE 4: INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

As the projects were being carried out in the 11 different settings, it proved challenging to be able to carry out an evaluation process with the young people and the facilitators.

However, after their involvement within the WYRED methodology, several participants asked if they could take on a further role within the process “and allow them to have “their say” as well”. These young people have become facilitators of different communities within the WYRED platform. As these young people continue to be involved within their own youth organisations in the 11 countries, many have made use of their experiences with WYRED to develop further research projects and events in their local communities. One facilitator highlighted how “the participants from Greece planned the future steps of their project: they made a deal with a radio station to air the podcasts in order to share their stories and give voice to a group that is unheard.”

4. Insights

4.1 Overview: Giving Away the Car Keys

The WYRED project provides a space for children and young people to engage in reflection about their digital lives. The nine partners have guided over 1000 children and young people over two years to ask questions and carry out research about themes and ideas that affect and shape their interactive, performative and communicative worlds. Through these efforts, the children and young people have navigated and mapped their way through an ever evolving landscape where their experience of growing up and maturing has been in many ways mediated by technological developments and experiments. Through WYRED, we have listened carefully and remained tuned into their critical analysis. As described by one young person, being involved in WYRED was like “being given the keys of the car and allowed to drive”.

These children and young people are as concerned about self-image and the ephemera of their social media accounts as much as they are with democracy, online activism and changing social structures. An analysis of the WYRED project work, whether completed or in progress, demonstrates an extremely sophisticated grasp of the interpersonal and intrapersonal relationships between technology, society and youth.

This document sets out some key insights as they are emerging from the work on the ground in each of countries, from within their formal, informal and non-formal learning environments.

Initially the WYRED methodological approach is described. The successful testing of this approach over two cycles of dialogues and research activities has allowed for the generation of results and answers to questions that were considered valuable by the children and young people.

The main themes are then examined, with a focus on relevant insights for stakeholders including decision makers and policy makers, schools and youth workers.

The six WYRED themes focus on:

- Self-image and its presentation online
- Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping
- Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security
- Living on social media, living with stress
- Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy
- Digital participation and activism, digital divide

WYRED research projects into the attitudes and perspectives of young people tend to demonstrate that the majority feel relatively optimistic about their own future, appreciating better access to educational opportunities and a better health outlook than their parents’ generations. However, the backdrop to this optimism can be considered an almost pervasive lack of faith in institutions and in politics. The children and

young people are concerned about their environment and democratic structures. However, they do not regard themselves as “radicals” when they are posing questions regarding our “grown-up” responses to the many existential threats that they are highlighting.

The WYRED projects highlight how these young people can shape and direct their online interactions, thereby appearing to enhance their autonomy and personal agency. However, they are also examining potential correlations between rates of depression amongst teenagers and time spent on social media. They are consistently displaying a sophisticated analysis of how they manage this balancing act between public and private narratives, positive and negative self-image and these interplays.

WYRED projects demonstrate the pleasure and stimulation to be found on screens and smartphones that unleash positive and creative urges. Through this engagement within the WYRED methodology, children and young people are exploring their potential in a myriad of new and exciting ways. However, the unlimited availability of social media outlets for viewing, content-creating, and editing also allows for constant exposure, social comparison and an on-demand culture. According to many of the WYRED contributors, online harassment and cyberbullying are considered to be facts of life. Through their research, they are examining ways of responding, from personal, group and institutional perspectives.

Whether the children and young people see themselves as digital natives living within a new culture, with the older generation somehow fundamentally different digital immigrants, the nuances of an intergenerational gap are to be found in the WYRED research activities. The children and young people are less inclined to draw distinctions between an online and offline existence. As members of a more digitally oriented social environment, they could still identify many structural factors presenting new challenges in relation to inclusion and equality. Such themes are explored, as well as the potential for digital participation as a strategy to counter racism, homophobia and transphobia. The children and young people also look to their “technology-rich culture” and examine whether it can work to inspire their skills and interests in relation to their formal education experiences.

The challenges and perceptions of older generations also receive attention within the WYRED research. A recent survey of parents in Northern Ireland has found that some two thirds of parents were more worried than hopeful about parenting in the future. Among their main concerns, parents identified the impacts of technology and social media on young people. The children and young people tend to have a strong awareness of these adult concerns. Through many research projects, they seek to better understand mental health issues or the management of stress. These exercises in research and critical analysis allow the children and young people to develop a balanced understanding of the both challenges and the opportunities presented by their digital world.

Through these WYRED project developments and responses, children and young people are articulating questions that they want to answer; they are expressing their desires; yet are acknowledging that they are often unsure or unaware of their vulnerabilities. There is a clear ambivalence that they are pointing to in terms of how

their online lives are being governed. The positive opportunities that are being put forward are in counterpoint to potential unhappiness, anxiety and lack of control.

This core ambivalence, represented by the new meanings and responses that the children and young people articulate as a reaction to their overlapping digital and social environments, represents an important insight that has emerged through our WYRED project.

If understanding ambivalence is the key, if a seemingly anti-reflection culture is emerging amongst children and young people, when given the opportunity by WYRED, what are these same children and young people actually reflecting upon?

4.2 The WYRED Methodology- How were the children and young people guided?

The WYRED methodological approach involves a series of linked phases.

1. This begins with a consultation phase involving outreach and engagement work and a social dialogue process. In this initial step, the children and young people are brought together and facilitated to examine digital society issues and concerns, using age appropriate facilitation techniques and tools.
2. This work leads to a second phase of research definition. Through the articulation of research questions, the children and young people are again supported to consider the key issues in more depth.
3. The next stage in the process involves an action dimension. The research question becomes articulated as a research project. This can take a wide range of forms, from the development of a video response, a podcast discussion, journaling or blogging, through to the writing of poetry.
4. These projects are then analysed in the final phase. The children young people look to interpret their work, their responses and attribute further meaning to these phases of work. At each phase, the children and young people are being empowered to present their own analysis and critique of the online environment with which they are dealing.

The project involved a series of Delphi consultation exercises, involving 206 young people and 69 stakeholders from different countries taking part in the first round, while 260 young people and 89 stakeholders participated in a second round. The results from both rounds highlight that young people consistently attribute the highest importance to the issues of “self-image and self-confidence”, “tolerance to different cultures/opinions”, and “necessary changes in education” as well as “mental wellbeing”. the opinions of stakeholders regarding the most important issues is are in general rather similar to those of the young people, except one noticeable difference: the stakeholders attribute much higher importance than young people to the issue of media literacy, namely the reliability of information on the internet and in social media. A further third round of Delphi style consultation work will allow for a comparative look at any emerging trends.

The development and application of the WYRED methodology operated over a series of interlinked cycles. Cycle 1 focused on the testing of this methodology with children and young people across the full partnership. This cycle led to the engagement of over 500 children and young people in a consultative process, leading in turn to 280 of these participating in over 100 separate projects. An online platform was developed to allow the sharing of these local projects and promote an engagement between the target groups and key policy stakeholders, from education, youth work and community sectors.

Cycle 2 allowed for further iterations of the methodological steps. Partners have again reached out to over 500 children and young people in consultative forums, facilitating conversations and discussions regarding perceptions about their online lives. Through these social dialogues, a further set of 58 research questions were elaborated, leading to a set of almost 50 projects with the involvement of over 300 children and young people. Again, these projects have led to the sharing of responses and presentations of solutions to commonly faced challenges within the platform and elsewhere.

Cycle 3 is continuing to further apply the methodology within a range of new settings, including youth centres working with disadvantaged children and young people.

Throughout these cycles, partners have focused on an examination of themes and topics of interest to children and young people related to digital society issues. The priority for WYRED projects was to draw out recommendations or conclusions from the children and young people around their chosen research projects and topics of interest.

In order to surface these insights, the children and young people were facilitated to evaluate their own projects through a range of creative methods, informal and dynamic approaches, as well as specifically tailored toolkits. These self-administered processes assisted the children and young people to identify the value and relevance of what they had been doing within WYRED activities. This was also a core element of the WYRED approach in ensuring that children and young people would be active in this process through choosing the messages, formats and channels that they regard as most appropriate to present their results, in relation to what it is that they want to explain and how they would present this. Evaluation toolkits were available for partners to implement and tailor in their local environments.

4.3 Reviewing this WYRED Methodology

The case studies in the previous section of the report present detail on how the methods and approaches were applied with a wide range of different age groups, within formal and informal spaces and educational settings and with larger and smaller groups. In many instances, the application of the methodology by a particular facilitator led to significant one-to-one supports being provided.

As described by one of the WYRED participants, the core principle of the methodology can be viewed as “giving them car keys and letting them drive”.

The facilitators, teachers and youth workers used the social dialogue phase of the process to explain and outline the thematic parameters of the project. The children and young people were brought together in schools, colleges, youth centres and facilities in over 20 countries. They were encouraged to ask the hard questions of the WYRED project, the facilitators and the process. As they came to realise that these thematic parameters were very flexible and that it was their own particular interests that would come to drive their further engagement, some participants would politely step away from the process.

However, the majority of over 600 children and young people chose to stay involved. They were now motivated and inspired to take active control over the process. Their facilitators became back seat passengers in this moving vehicle. Through this process of taking charge of their learning and shaping the questions that they wanted to research, the children and young people became their own agents of change.

The phases of research definition and implementation took a wide range of shapes and turns. Poetry was written, photography exhibits were put together, models were built, site visits were made to NGOs and others with expertise to offer, questionnaires were developed, interviews were carried out. Through it all, the children and young people were in the driving seat. When they needed some support in addressing their research question or unpacking a difficult hypothesis, they would first ask each other and then if required, the WYRED facilitator would step in.

It is clear that from the experience of being active participants within this research process that the children and young people were allowed to develop their own voice, ask their own questions and formulate their own responses. Through this process of being “handed the keys”, they were empowered to take charge. They could progress an agenda that was set themselves. Whether this was linked to an interest in big themes associated with climate change or democracy, racism or homophobia, they were motivated to direct their work and make arguments, conclusions and recommendations that were shared and disseminated across a wide range of forums. When their interest was linked more locally or specifically to themes regarding social media representations and impacts of influencers, they were equally able to articulate sophisticated research questions that led to important insights that could be shared widely.

The children and young people found a range of ways to present their findings. Their peers were involved, their teachers and youth workers were key targets, policy-makers and decision-makers were also engaged. Family members were invited to dissemination activities. Schools and colleges made changes to policies and procedures as a result of WYRED projects. Young people travelled to events across Europe, in which they were invited to present recommendations or participate in high level committees. Some of these events were attended by European Commission representatives, politicians within the House of Lords, delegates from national policy conferences and networking forums. The children and young people were facilitated to see that their action research should have an intended outcome. For many of the WYRED projects, these outcomes were met.

4.4 Role of the WYRED Platform: Building a Body of Work and Shared Ideas

The WYRED platform allows for children and young people to share their projects, their experiences and thoughts. There are specific conversation threads and thematic areas in which conversations can happen. There is also the repository and archive of individual and group projects, their resulting artefacts, outputs and stories. Each separate presentation, spreadsheet, research report, video or podcast has been shared within an international community of children and young people.

As these WYRED research results are grouped according to digital themes and associated tags, participants new to WYRED can search this archive and get ideas for future work.

Ongoing conversations are facilitated through the platform. These can be synchronous, with students in different countries coming together for live discussions or asynchronous, where children and young people can watch videos back and share their responses. The success of these engagements is linked to the fact that the children and young people are setting their agenda; they have been supported to “drive the car” themselves.

The platform is open to children and young people, once a registration step has taken place.

4.5 Thematic Insights

This section reviews feedback from participants and facilitators with regards to their experience of being involved in a selected sample of 51 WYRED projects. In relation to each of the six themes, any lessons or considerations for future WYRED directions are presented. These 51 projects involved some 419 children and young people, aged from 9 to 23 years of age, with over half aged 16-19 years of age.

The children and young people selected and developed research projects under the following themes:

WYRED Digital Theme Focus	Proportion of Projects (51)	Proportion of Participants (419)
Self-image and its presentation online	12%	9%
Gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping	14%	22%
Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security	16%	17%
Living on social media, living with stress	16%	22%
Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy	12%	9%
Digital participation and activism, digital divide	31%	22%
Total	100%	100%

In relation to the theme of *Self-image and its presentation online*, children and young people were keen to focus on the construction of individual identities, offline and online. Key words that emerge are linked to vulnerability,

stigma and stereotype. Participants were motivated to look at strategies as to how positive self-image can be promoted, at the level of the individual, but also at group or classroom level.

The process of working together on this theme encouraged some groups to compare their local realities. The sharing of experiences in relation to how these young people manage and consider their “online self” acted as an empowering process. One young person highlighted that “it feels like we can actually talk and people will actually hear us and together work to change”.

An important insight that emerged through the feedback is linked to the importance of forging resilience not out of toughness and adversity, but through maintaining a relationship with one’s self that contains self-belief and accuracy. Through supporting this inner resilience, the group will also benefit.

The development of research questions and projects that focused on the theme of *gender discrimination, and gender differences online, stereotyping* was carried out by over 20% of WYRED participants. The manner in which offline gender stereotypes can be reinforced within online activities and platforms was studied by young people. Through addressing research questions in this area, young people looked to understand differences across countries and cultures. An important insight is offered by participants who presented research in this theme:

“Gender roles put pressure not only on women but also on men. The lifestyle which forces men to be macho and masculine makes them brutal, strict, and prone to violence. Gender inequities and employment discrimination continue in education, politics, law enforcement, business, medicine, media, the military, and religion. Creative contributions of women are less encouraged and recognized than are those of men in many areas such as the arts and sciences. Women still suffer negative effects of discrimination in quality of life outcomes related to their safety and employment and leadership of government and business organisations.”

Within this theme, children and young people returned to the manner in which individual identities are constructed and the fact that it depends on a large number of external and internal factors. Within the construction of online identities, the pressures to conform to idealised notions represents a shared challenge for young women, evidenced across WYRED research results in different countries, age groups and settings.

The impacts of cyberbullying and hacking were research topics within the theme of *Internet safety and privacy, cyberbullying, online abuse and cyber security*. Children and young people felt that they were used now to receiving regular guidance and tips about how and why to stay safe online, in terms of possible threats as well as to Internet security issues. While many children and young people were often surprised by their research findings in this area, many felt that there should also be greater awareness-raising for parents, teachers and youth workers.

This insight is important in terms of how the voice of the young person should be included in examining how best to address a situation of cyberbullying. There was found to be a range of different parental, school or institutional responses that led to some confusion. Conclusions point to the many challenges that remain to be

addressed in this area of cyberbullying. It is recommended that the voice of children and young people are included in the response. A teacher from one WYRED project highlighted the following:

“Bullying today takes place mainly on social media but the effects are visible in real life. Students have identified a bullied person as someone who is possibly introverted, isolated and weak. At national level, schools are creating partnerships with the police to train young people about the use of Internet and its laws, but young people affirm that schools should have a more direct role in terms of inclusion, support and direct confrontation. Teachers, instead affirm that for them is quite difficult to detect the phenomenon in class.”

Many of the younger cohorts within this research theme were increasingly aware about potential pitfalls in the management of personal data. Having this information at a younger age was regarded as important as these children begin to access mobile phones and the range of popular platforms.

An insight from a facilitator in dealing with the theme of *Living on social media, living with stress*, is particularly illustrative: “Never before have we had more Mental Health Awareness, Yet never before have we been more unhappy.” Over 20% of WYRED participants elaborated projects in this area. How children and young people deal with the performative aspect of their online lives represents an important focus here. They point to a range of pressures and how they need to respond. This creates and sustains stress.

“Young people need to perform, they have to accomplish good grades, in some schools nothing else is left but learning for tests and other achievements. This produces stress and makes sick, only the strong survive seems to be the motto. Isn't it just that these young people simply follow the current trends of society. Everybody has to perform on the highest levels and as no one can do so constantly, everybody is individually responsible to work on her or his resilience. But these young people know it better, besides individual aspects, of coping with stress (mental training, sports, nutrition) they also identify the school structures (tests and homework) which produce stress for so many of them and need to be changed.”

A teacher again highlights the point as to how stress can build up through school factors and then become amplified by social media:

“School and evaluation is one of the main origins of stress in young people. Using social media can make young people feel unsatisfied as they compare their lives with those of others and doing what others do instead of taking the time and space to find their identity. This can cause further stress and unhappiness.”

These pressures are noted across many different WYRED projects. Young people understand that they can lead to more stress within a social media vacuum that requires constant perfection.

To counter this, young people deliver insights regarding the importance of developing coping mechanisms and understanding resilience from a younger age. Such lifeskills can then allow the child or young person develop

their online identity in a positive manner. Understanding this performative aspect of a social media identity is important for the other stakeholders in the life of child or young person.

Children and young people are clearly also able to recognise positive opportunities presented by their social media presence. They can readily share information and thoughts. Their relationships within their social group can be mediated in a positive manner, allowing for new dynamics to emerge. Many of the young people highlighted that they wanted to always be “critical consumers of technology, not just sheep”.

Fake news represented a key area of interest for children and young people within the theme of *Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy*. The youngest cohorts of WYRED participants carried out research into this area, quizzing their peers with regard to how they might understand what is real and what is false with regard to media representations of events. They sought to understand how news stories are reported and interpreted. Their analysis highlighted the importance of trusting information sources. Within an online environment, this is increasingly challenging.

The largest set of projects undertaken were in relation of the theme of *Digital participation and activism, digital divide*. Almost one third of all projects were associated with better understanding digital divides, across countries and classes. Many young people were interested in how future developments would impact on these divides. Within education and employment, they point to uncertainty and vulnerability. The digital world can be potentially seen to further entrench a range of disadvantages. One project highlights concerns regarding the impact of external structural factors affect social and economic participation.

“We focused on young people's perception of future in relation to employment uncertainty. The results of the survey administered to young people from high schools to young workers show that the high unemployment standards have scared our youth population and with regret everyone dreams to move abroad as soon as possible. Few people know about the meaning of education and training, meaning that they are sometimes not aware of their condition, therefore they don't advocate for policy change.”

Many young people focused on how best to use new media to energise and develop new responses to these structural factors. The development of local community level or school-based campaigns has been made easier through access to digital tools.

One group used the opportunity of participating in a WYRED project to start conversations using online tools about issues associated with immigration. They presented an important insight about the importance of creating a meaningful space where discussion can be mediated positively:

“What is missing is a genuine and fruitful online discussion, where different communities can enter in contact and know better each other. Because, nowadays people talk too much without knowing the truth, and ignorance can bring people to believe to fake news and is the basis for the rise of racist and discriminatory messages. This space will be needed to properly use social media and online platforms and where information should be gathered.”

These discussions led to new relationships being formed with other young people in their community and the development of podcasts and shared projects. Creative approaches to promoting community learning can be supported by such online approaches. Key within this type of communicative response is the recognition that digital exclusion represents a real fear for children and young people, thus mirroring and reinforcing social and economic exclusion.

Children and young people were mostly engaged in digital activism in order to promote awareness raising in terms of a positive environmental message. These children and young people expressed that fighting against climate change for them is not a radical proposition. Using positive online platforms and opportunities can work to break down social divides and change people's attitudes. Using many such WYRED projects, children and young people have articulated many common points in their value systems that involve a nuanced and sophisticated understanding of their online world. One facilitator highlighted that the children and young people had espoused a value that "in a culture of offence and distraction we need to instil balance, calm and space."

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